

Interaction of Childhood Traumas and Depression

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-10, 2023, p. 110– 113. - 0099-0001-2310-1005.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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Current Science

Article Application

Date: Article Publication

Date: Article Type: Review

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Abstract

Trauma is a concept that is used for all the situations that shock, hurt and injure a person's spiritual and physical presence in various different ways. In order for the situation to be considered as trauma, the child must assume it as a threat for his or some other person's life or physical integrity; or he must be face to face with death or subjected to violence. Sometimes the child perceives the situation differently than as it actually is. The important criteria here is how the child records the situation.

Traumas may be grouped as, physical abuse, emotional abuse, sexual abuse, emotional neglect and physical neglect.

Traumas may cause several different kinds of disorders or health problems if they are not treated. Especially

isolation, withdrawal, problems of communication and depression may be observed in the future years of the child. Cognitive problems, tendency to crime and aggressive attitudes are seen quite frequently as well.

Depression is a mental disorder that is characterized by sadness, lack of pleasure, displaying sleeping and eating disorders. Other symptoms may be poor concentration and tiredness.

Some types of traumas are: Disruptive mood dysregulation disorder, persistent depression disorder and major depression disorder. During all these disorders negative emotional mode is dominant.

The children who have experienced trauma are affected cognitively, emotionally, psychologically and neurobiologically. Their neural pathways have changed so; depression disorders may manifest more likely in them as well as the other psychological disorders and other health problems.

Key words: Trauma, physical abuse, emotional abuse, sexual abuse, emotional neglect, physical neglect, depression, disruptive mood regulation disorder, persistent depression disorder, major depression disorder

Introduction

Being subjected to abuse physically or emotionally influences the child profoundly and shakes his beliefs about the world. Parenthood is an arduous job that requires attention, tolerance, compassion and patience. Sometimes simply the most basic situations, words or attitudes may be recorded negatively in the child's mind. The parents may cause traumas consciously or unconsciously. Sometimes traumas are because of natural disasters, or they may be because of various different situations such as; divorce, changing cities, to move to another house, having another baby. Sometimes a trauma may occur outside the house because of another child's attitude. Trauma may be caused by sexual or physical abuse of a relative or another person outside home. In all these situations the parents, the caregivers and the teacher must be alert and must be aware of the child's attitudes and emotions. They should not overlook any details. If the traumas are detected and the child is treated properly, the effects and the symptoms may be healed. Otherwise the child may experience a lot of difficult psychological and physical disorders. The child's life may be full of adversity because he wouldn't have resolved what he

had lived and his mind will be stuck in the past trauma. One of the most common disorders that is experienced is depression. There is precisely an interaction between traumas and depression cognitively, emotionally, psychologically and neurobiologically.

Trauma

Trauma is a word and concept that is used for all the situations that shocks, hurts and wounds the spiritual and physical presence of people. Trauma may occur because of natural disasters or it may occur human-induced as well. The factor that separates trauma from the other challenging events that can be experienced throughout life is that; the person perceives that tough event as a threat for his or another person's life or body integrity. The person's becoming face to face with death or his being exposed to violence causes trauma. Trauma is unexpected, extraordinary and out of control. It may have occurred only for once and unrepeated or it may be ongoing and multiple. (Mayda & Yücel, 2021)

According to DSM-V (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders) ; in

In order for a situation to be a trauma it has to have some criteria: The person's becoming face to face with a situation that directly threatens his or a friend or a relative's physical integrity or individuality. The person comes face to face with the tough situation many times and perceives the situation as disturbing. After all these, the person feels guilty together with the sensation of despair, horror and fear. (Mayda & Yücel, 2021, p 13).

We may group traumas as; physical abuse, emotional abuse, sexual abuse, emotional neglect and physical neglect.

Physical abuse is the general name for the risky attitudes that cause wounds and damage to the body. The most frequently seen physical abuses are bruises, burnt or broken body parts that are caused by hitting and beating. Drowning and poisoning are also encountered. Every kind of abuse that hurts the child such as pulling his hair or ear, locking him in a room are considered as physical abuse. All these processes affect the child psychologically, cognitively and spiritually. Resorting to violence is in a way expressing anger and providing authority by using

punishing systems. These parents or care-givers are people that have no control of themselves and they precisely do not have realistic expectations from their children.

Emotional abuses are making fun of, belittling, rejecting and refusing the child and using hurtful words. The harmful degree of effect of the abuse changes according to the age of the child. The relations of the children that are exposed to emotional abuse are negatively affected. Emotional abuse is meaningfully related with some kinds of personality disorders and depression as well.

An adult's making use of a child in order to fulfill his sexual needs and pleasure is sexual abuse. Sexually explicit messages and phone calls, exhibitionism and taking off

the child's clothes are characterized as sexual abuse as well. To touch the child's body

and try to intercourse with the child is the most violent sexual abuse. The children, the parents and the teachers should be educated in this context and the children should learn how to defend their body integrity whereas the parents and the teachers learn how to support the children if they face these kinds of tough situations.

The damage that is given to the child by not meeting his clothing and nutritional requirements is called physical neglect. Shelter is one of the most important needs of a child. Not sheltering the child securely, kicking him out of home, and excluding him, are physical neglect. If the child has a health problem and he is not provided with a treatment, if his washing and cleaning requirements are not met, these are considered physical neglect as well. Physical neglect may be overlooked easily, because; this problem is not apparent as physical abuse; however it is as important as it.

Physical neglect predicts; isolation, withdrawal, problems of communication and depression in the future years of the child. Cognitive problems, tendency to crime and aggressive attitudes are seen quite frequently as well. Physical abuse and physical neglect mostly occur together and unfortunately causes new abuse and neglect. If the parents or the caregivers have experienced physical abuse or physical neglect in their own childhood, or if they have psychological disorders or substance abuse, there is more risk for them to cause physical abuse or physical neglect. (Mayda & Yücel, 2021).

In order to measure the childhood traumas, many kinds of scales have been used in psychological evaluations. These scales measure and evaluate; Physical and emotional abuse, sexual abuse and physical and emotional neglect.

What Cause Traumas?

Our judgments about ourselves are formed during early childhood. These experiences predict what kind of a person we are going to be when we grow up. Little children consider their parents or their caregivers perfect, strong people that know everything and never make any mistake. Because of that if the child is a subject of any kind of abuse or neglect, he assumes that he himself is the guilty one. He thinks: 'If these perfect people do any mistake, I must have done something wrong and I deserve this attitude'. He thinks 'They are very thoughtful in fact, and I must have been a child that didn't deserve being loved'. (Markham, 1998).

Traumas may sometimes not be anyone's fault, they may be caused by natural disasters or they may innocently stem from only not knowing, not noticing. For example if one of the parents or caregivers go to the hospital without making any explanations, if the child gets lost and can't find his parents even for a short period, these may cause traumas. If someone from his family dies and the duration is not managed properly, divorcing of the parents if again can't be managed properly may cause traumas as well. If any health problems occur and anxiety can't be managed properly, these may cause traumas too.

On the other hand while a tough discipline may harm the child, discipline deprived life may give more harm to the child. To know the rules and his limits always provides a better and more secure life for the child. Sometimes the child may not feel he is loved enough. He feels he is not entitled to be loved and considers himself as guilty because of this. These kinds of children feel unworthiness and lack of self-confidence as they grow up. These feelings easily cause depression and many other kinds of problems. (Markham, 2021)

Some parents and caregivers belittle and criticize children more than necessary and assume that in this way their children will try to reach their goals and they will make more efforts. However, criticizing and judging children may cause traumas. Especially if the parents use some hurtful words, the children's self-confidence may be damaged.

Another important subject that may cause harm to the children is to give hard tasks according to his age and capacity. Punishments must be balanced according to the child's fault. If he is punished harshly compared to what he had done, his self-respect and self-confidence will be low when he grows up. This causes him depression as well.

Something that parents do that they shouldn't is comparing the child with his sister or brother. This is one of the things that shouldn't be done to a child. If the child is objected to in such conditions, he will not love his brother and worse than this, he will believe he is less valuable than his brother.

The children who are subjected to such attitudes may become isolated from society. They may try to take revenge from the world that injured him by addressing violence. They may have eating disorders or sleeping problems. They may have psychological disorders, have depression and cannot maintain a normal life. (Markham, 2021, p: 97)

Depression

Depression is an emotional mode in which a person doesn't feel himself well psychologically, that may continue for a period of time and affect the flow of his life.

Lack of motivation, feeling of worthlessness, pessimism, unhappiness, feeling of guilt, thoughts of death and suicide are some of the symptoms of depression.

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According to DSM-5, there are different types of depression disorders: 1. Disruptive mood dysregulation disorder, 2. Persistent depression disorder, 3. Major depression disorder. During all these disorders negative emotional mode is dominant and there is no manic episode. (Arkar, 2022)

Disruptive mood dysregulation disorder may begin at the age of 6-10. According to the American Psychiatric Association, the two most specific symptoms of this disorder is; violent outburst anger and angry and irritable mood. The frequency of anger is at least three times a week and duration of the mode is at least twelve months. (Arkar, 2021).

The outburst of anger is inconsistent with the developmental level. The emotional mood of anger may be observed by parents, teachers or friends. The anger mode lasts consecutively at least three months. The symptoms are observed at least at the two of the environments of school, home and friends, specially at one of them the symptoms manifest themselves intensely. These symptoms must be explained only with this disorder and not because of the other health problems.

Persistent depression disorder manifests itself as an uneasy mental state. It affects social relations, academic performance and the flow of life. The symptoms may be chronic, mild, moderate or intense and last at least for a year for children and for two years for adults. For this type of disorder the emphasis is on the persistence rather than the severity. During childhood, even the least depressive disorders must be considered and taken over and shouldn't be overlooked, because they predict major depressive episodes afterwards in adulthood. These early depressions are less likely to be healed.

According to DSM-4, this disorder was named dysthymia, and the definition of the symptoms were a little bit different. Now according to the new definition of the symptoms of DSM-5 some of the symptoms observed must be decrease in appetite, overeating, inability to sleep or oversleeping, low energy level or feeling of tiredness, low self-perception, strain in focusing attention or difficulty in making decisions and feeling of hopelessness.

Major depression disorder is differentiated from disruptive mood dysregulation disorder by the symptoms by some characteristics. This type of disorder indicates

outburst of intense and persistent rage and irritableness rather than episodic mood changes in the disruptive mood dysregulation disorder. The complementary features of the disorder are depressive emotional state and loss of pleasure in the daily routines (anhedonia). This is an acute situation that lasts at least for two weeks.

According to DSM-5, in order to diagnose this kind of disorder at least five of the symptoms among nine, must be observed in the patient These symptoms are:

1. Assuming negative self-concept about himself about his appearance, attitudes and intelligence, such as 'I'm ugly, I'm stupid or I'm clumsy'.
2. They have difficulty expressing their feelings. If for example they don't want to go to the school, instead of expressing this feeling they prefer explaining their somatic complaints as tiredness, headache or stomachache.
3. They refuse spending time with their peers, performing in any kind of activities and hobbies, they feel isolated from the society.
4. He prefers staying in his room alone and sleeping continuously. If he has to interact with the family members, he displays nervous attitudes.
5. They have an anger outburst when they are refused or criticized, and they cry.
6. They have eating and drinking disorders.
7. They dispose of attitudes of anger outburst.
8. They have death and suicide thoughts.
9. They have phobias and anxiety.

(Arkar, 2022)

In order to treat depression, an accurate evaluation must be made. There are some tools in hand for this evaluation. There are various purposeful scales, however it requires attention in order to choose the proper procedure. Clinicians diagnose depression by synthesizing the information they got from the patient, by the results of the scales and their own data they observed about the patient. So this synthesis is a product of mixed evaluations. (Wells & Fisher, 2022)

Depression may be measured by different kinds of scales. Beck's Depression Inventory (BDI), the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales, the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS) and Zung Self-Rating Depression Scale are some of them. These are not diagnostic tools however, they support the assessment. They help determine the severity of the level of the depression.

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Interactions among childhood traumas and depression

Negative thoughts, feelings and situations and traumas cause rumination, negative

thoughts and beliefs about the self and then cause depression. Stress of the trauma influences the schemas and the metacognitive thoughts, so it influences the ability to deal with the hardships of life. These useless thought patterns cause depression and as well new ruminations. This endures as a cycle. (Wells & Fisher, 2022, p: 145).

The structure of the brain of the children who are subjected to neglect and abuse changes by the influence of threat and lackness. This structure becomes excessively active because of stress and abnormal levels of hormone secretion. All these changes reflect their adolescence and adulthood periods. Stress and trauma's effects must be addressed both cognitively, emotionally, psychologically and neurobiologically. Brain changes neurobiologically by being subjected to stress and trauma. (Kolk, 2018)

Depression as well causes neurobiological changes in the brain. For example, the blood flow and the metabolism of the amygdala that has connections with the ventrolateral and lateral prefrontal cortex decreases. Some anomalies are observed at the depressed patients' hippocampus. The volume of the hippocampus decreases. Anomalies may be observed at the structure of the basal ganglia that has a connection with the cerebral cortex and caudate and putamen. So it is seen that traumas and depression influence the brain structure in a similar way. However if the depression is treated in a successful way, the patterns may change in the reverse direction. The blood flow at the cortical areas is observed to be increased. (Wells & Fisher, 20022, p: 89)

Conclusion and Discussion

Being subjected to trauma causes many clinical effects such as anxiety, phobias, depression, learning problems, eating and drinking disorders, addictions, manias, suicide attempts, sexual

problems or psychosis. It is very common for a person to experience psychological problems as he grows up if he is subjected to any kind of trauma in his early years. Some symptoms they experience are; depression, dissociation, distractibility and behavioral problems. It is also recorded that decreases in their social abilities and cognitive capabilities are also observed.

Cognitive processes are influenced by trauma and evolve in a different way. The memory about the trauma combines with various different emotions while they are being transferred to the mind. Whenever any new event happens, any memory that evokes the trauma is recalled and fear, anger and despair emotions are manifested as reactions.

There are some predisposing risk factors that may ignite and feed the trauma instead of calming down and healing it. The person's illnesses, if he has any, mental capacity, communication skills and some personality features may feed the negative situation and cause a decrease in the performance of the patient while he is getting treatment. Obligatory migration, popping up a sudden illness and unexpected loss are as well triggering factors that affect the depression treatment.

However there may be supporting factors as well such as; the patient's getting support from his environment socially, having strong relations with the family members and friends, having steady support from social and economic sources. (Aktan, 2021)

Being mindful about his traumas and his wounds and to be aware of his mindset gives the patient the opportunity to perceive the positive sides and handle his situation more easily. In order to help the person or a child he must be given some time to get ready and prepare a base for his healing.

Limitations

This research is limited to the extent of the data in the world literature. The research is restricted to the research about the related subjects. It is limited to literature surveys.

Notices

Assessment: This study was assessed by internal and external advisors.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declared no conflicts of interest in relation to this article.

Financial Support: The author declared no financial support for the investigation of this research.

Ethical Declaration

This study aims to ensure that scientific research is made in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, respect for the findings and creations of others and aims to realize these principles in the field of related disciplines.

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